

Beyond the Surface – Exploring and Defining Indirect Risks in Clinical Free-text

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Introduction

The provision of clinical free-text for research necessitates care to address identifiable information. Current published work focuses on addressing privacy risks, such as names, addresses etc., and is modelled on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) categories [1]. In our work we define these types of risks as direct, however, there are more indirect risks that exist. Indirect risks differ in that they are more implicit within clinical records, such as details about where a medical event took place, family and living circumstances, all of which could reveal someone's identity, particularly when patient records are combined. Stubbs et al. [2] highlight these indirect risks in their data, which focuses on psychiatry notes and is prepared for public release to be used in a de-identification task. However, they remove the indirect risks and focus only on direct categories of risks. One of the main reasons indirect risks are not well researched is the lack of publicly available data.

Our work was a pilot study to explore what types of risks beyond direct identifiers exist, and how these could be categorised, to gain a better understanding and focus research attention on these areas.

Methods and Data

Indirect privacy risks are rare in the context of clinical records, which makes them hard to find. However, clinical records have a certain amount of repetition in the way clinicians write about patients with the same disease, outcome, treatment, etc. Our approach was to use sentence similarity with hierarchical clustering to explore patterns that expose indirect risks. We pre-processed reports into sentences and applied BERT Topic modelling [3] at a sentence level, using similarity measures to cluster sentences together. We labelled the topics using class-based TF-IDF (see Figure 1, an example of sentence clusters and labels). These topic labels were manually reviewed for any that may contain privacy risks and for those that did we subsequently read the sentences and their reports. This qualitative approach allowed us to direct our attention to those records with proportionately more risks.

Data: We extracted one year's worth of hospital discharge summaries for 2022, from three major hospitals in NHS Lothian, for patients with admission to a hospital ward with a >24 hours stay; this resulted in approximately 89,000 reports. Data was split across age ranges of patients, 18-30, 31-50, 51-70 and 71+. NHS Lothian utilises structured templates, which can be inserted by clinicians when typing up discharge summaries. These templates were used to find and reduce the data e.g. removing drug lists or uninformative headers and footers from templates.

Results

Privacy Risks: From our review of clusters and subsequent reports we created 6 main categories of indirect privacy risks: *Unique Medical Events/Rare and Sensitive Diseases; Social; Locations & Organisations; Mental Health; Police; Crime* (see Figure 2 for further descriptions of these). From our observations often where one of these categories occur within one sentence in a report, many of the other categories could subsequently be found in that report. The occurrence of risks differed across age ranges and the cumulative effect of how often a patient attended could increase the risk of identifiability. Whilst it is not surprising to find these types of categories in reports it does, however, highlight that care needs to be taken to consider privacy concerns beyond currently published work on direct identifiers.

Figure 1 Example of cluster found within the discharge summary

Figure 2 Indirect privacy risk categories

Conclusion

We have undertaken an exploration of discharge summaries to expand the knowledge of privacy risk categories to include indirect risks. We have characterised these risks into broad categories. Raising awareness of these risks promotes better understanding of the challenges in preparing data for research access. Developing better understanding will support more work in de-risking health records and underpins future data access for the NLP health text community.

Limitations: the data used is within one health board, year, and type of report. Further work is needed to expand this. The challenging part is further work can only be undertaken by data custodians. Highlighting these types of risks though, could provide direction around synthetic data work to support privacy risk research.

Our future work is considering how these risks can be addressed through NLP.

Study Context

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